

Studies in Ring Formation. Part II. The Constitution of Mono-phthalyl-benzidine.

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The present investigation is a continuation of the work of Sircar and De (this *Journal*, 1926, 3, 245) and undertaken with the object of studying how far Kaufler's formula (*Annalen*, 1907, 351, 151) for diphenyl and its derivatives could be supported.*

Gustav Koller (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 2880) condensed one molecule of benzidine with one molecule of phthalic anhydride and, from the insolubility of the resulting product in acids, concluded that both the amino groups in benzidine took part in the reaction. This view about the constitution of mono-phthalyl-benzidine was accepted and claimed by Kaufler (*loc. cit.*) as a strong proof in support of his theory.

It has now been found that, though insoluble in acids, Koller's mono-phthalyl-benzidine contains a free amino group. This has been proved by condensing the amino group with (1) various aldehydes, (2) another molecule of phthalic anhydride, (3) diazotising the amino group and coupling with β -naphthol.

These results establish the constitution of Koller's mono-phthalyl-benzidine to be

and not

EXPERIMENTAL.

Benzylidene-phthalyl-benzidine.

* The experimental work described in this and the two following papers was finished in March, 1926, and the present authors had no chance of knowing anything about the work of Fevre and Turner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 2476) in the same line. The communication has been delayed due to certain unavoidable reasons.

To a solution of phthalyl-benzidine (1 g.) of Koller (*loc. cit.*) in 25 c.c. of hot nitrobenzene, benzaldehyde (0.5 g.) was added and the mixture boiled under reflux for half an hour. The crystals which separated on cooling were washed with alcohol and purified by recrystallisation from nitrobenzene. It forms rectangular, light-yellow plates, m.p. above 300°.

It is insoluble in alcohol, benzene, acetic acid or pyridine, but soluble in nitrobenzene. It is easily hydrolysed by acids or alkalis. This is evident from the smell of the aldehyde evolved on heating the substance for sometime with acids or alkalis. (Found : N, 7.50. $C_{17}H_{13}O_2N_2$ requires N, 6.96 per cent.).

Hydroxy-benzylidene-phthalyl-benzidine was prepared in the same way as the preceding compound from phthalyl-benzidine (1 g.) and salicylic aldehyde (0.6 g.) and obtained as yellow needles (from nitrobenzene), m.p. 297°. It resembles the previous compound in its properties. (Found : N, 6.85. $C_{17}H_{13}O_3N_2$ requires N, 6.7 per cent.).

Fevre and Turner (*loc. cit.* p. 2482) have also described this and the preceding compound, but the methods of preparation and purification are somewhat different.

m-Nitrobenzylidene-phthalyl-benzidine, prepared in the same way (boiling for 15 minutes) as the preceding compounds, from phthalyl benzidine (1 g.) and *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (0.8 g.), separated from nitrobenzene in yellow needles, m.p. 280°. (Found : N, 9.52. $C_{17}H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N, 9.39 per cent.).

Phthalyl-4-aminodiphenyl-4'-azo-β-naphthol,

Phthalyl-benzidine (0.5 g.) was thoroughly triturated with 5 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid and then 20 c.c. of water added. The diazotisation was done in the usual way, the temperature of the reaction mixture being maintained at 20-22°. β-Naphthol (0.24 g.), dissolved in excess of caustic soda was then added to the diazotised solution. The resulting deep red, distinctly alkaline solution was left overnight. Next day the solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid when the azo-dye separated as a deep red precipitate. This was filtered, washed with water, dried and finally purified by successive crystallisations from alcohol, acetic acid and nitrobenzene. Microscopic crystals, m.p. 273-275°.

It is sparingly soluble in ether, more soluble in alcohol or acetic acid and easily soluble in pyridine or nitrobenzene. It dissolves in dilute caustic alkalis. (Found : N, 8.52. $C_{30}H_{18}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.95 per cent.).

Fevre and Turner (*loc. cit.*) have also described, in a qualitative way, the formation of such an azo-dye.

Di-p-diphthalyl-benzidine,

This was obtained by boiling a solution of phthalyl-benzidine (0.5 g.) and phthalic anhydride (0.25 g.) in 25 c.c. of nitrobenzene for two hours and separated from hot nitrobenzene as yellow plates not melting below 300°. It is found to be identical with Bandrowski's diphthalyl benzidine (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 1181).

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